

**TEACHERS' KNOWLEDGE AND SKILLS IN DEVELOPING
AND UTILIZING AUDIO-VISUAL INSTRUCTIONAL RESOURCES IN
TEACHING AND LEARNING ORAL LITERATURE IN SELECTED
PUBLIC SECONDARY SCHOOLS IN KENYA**

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Abstract:

Performance of pupils in Oral Literature examinations in English Paper 2 has been below average in recent years. For instance, the 2016 KCSE examination student performance in English was poor across the country and Butere Sub County in particular. Therefore, this research sought to determine teachers' knowledge and skills in developing and utilizing audio-visual instructional resources in teaching and learning oral literature in selected public secondary schools. The respondents for the study involved principals and oral literature teachers who were selected through purposive and stratified random sampling technique. The research instruments used were questionnaires and interview guides. The result of the analysis showed that despite most teachers attaining the required academic qualification, they did not adequately improvise audio-visual instructional resources during teaching and learning of oral literature in public secondary schools in Butere Sub County, Kenya. Oral literature teachers did not involve students in improvising these resources and this could be the underutilisation of audio-visual instructional resources in teaching and learning Oral Literature in secondary schools. The study recommends that principals in secondary need to ensure that OL is allocated time in the school timetable and also support teachers for further in-service training on audio-visual instructional media use in schools.

Keywords: audio-visual, improvisation, involvement, knowledge and skills

1. Introduction

The quality of education in Kenya faces a lot of challenges (Kanaga, 2010). To meet the challenges revisions of the curriculum are often mounted. The curriculum changes of the year 2002 resulted in the inclusion of teaching Oral Literature in the syllabus. One of the goals of teaching oral literature is to provide for respect for the development of Kenya's rich and varied cultures (KIE, 2002). This can be achieved through the teaching of Oral Literature because it is assumed in oral literature the Kenyan culture can be expressed better. The use of audio – visual resources would then be used to present content more accurately (KNEC, 2007, 2008). Audio-visual instructional materials are meant to impart knowledge to students in the educational process (Dahar & Faize, 2011). There has been increased outcry from educators on the poor performance of students in English for the past years (Butere District Quality Assurance and Standards Office [DQASO], 2011). It has been argued that low performance of students in English Kenya Certificate of Secondary Education (KCSE) paper (Kenya National Examination Council [KNEC], 2008) could be attributed to inadequate number of teachers and lack of educational instructional resources. Oral literature is an integrated component in English and therefore the audio-visual instructional resources constitute a critical component in teaching and learning the subject. According to Luvisia (2003), there are three factors that determine the quality of teaching and learning. These are physical facilities, competent teachers and adequacy of instructional media resources. Luvisia (2003), argues that availability of adequate instructional resources, physical facilities and competent teachers are prerequisites to quality teaching and by extension learning. A lot has been written and said about language being a very important medium of communication (Mackay Report 1981; Wanjuki, 2000; Rotumoi, 2006; Dahar & Faize, 2011). Since Oral Literature creates an opportunity for language use it is important that Oral Literature as part of English language should be promoted. This is because competence in English can be evident in the effective use of or as a result of the application of Oral Literature genres such as proverbs, wise sayings and oral poetry by high school students. Nevertheless, the competence of teachers through their knowledge and skills will lead to adoption and utilization of audio-visual resources in schools. It was due to the above reasons that this paper analyses the teachers' knowledge and skills in utilisation of audio-visual instructional resources in teaching and learning of Oral Literature subject secondary schools in Butere Sub-County Kenya.

2. Statement of the Problem

The continuous poor performance of high school students in English (Paper 2) where OL is an integrated component has attracted a lot of concern from the education

stakeholders' (Rotumoi, 2006; Luvisia, 2003; Wanjuki, 2000). Moreover, the released 2016 KCSE examinations showed poor performance by students across the country in English subject and Butere Sub County in particular. This creates the need for a solution to the poor performance. Teacher knowledge and skills in developing and utilisation of audio-visual instructional resources is critical in the explanation for poor academic performance of students in the subject in Butere Sub County schools. However, the literature reviewed indicates that a solution may not be easily identified because there is no previous study in the Sub County and Kenya on teachers' knowledge and skills on utilization of the instructional resources for Oral Literature. It is against this background that the paper addresses teachers' knowledge and skills in developing and utilizing audio-visual instructional resources in teaching and learning Oral Literature in selected secondary schools within Butere Sub County, Kenya.

3. Significance of the Study

This study is significant because it seeks to provide empirical data at a regional level on the important issue of teacher effectiveness with regard to utilisation and improvisation of audio-visual teaching resources in teaching and learning of oral literature in schools. The findings of this study are important to the government of Kenya (GOK) especially KIE and MoE, Oral Literature teachers, colleges, universities, individual secondary schools across the country and future researchers. On colleges and universities, the knowledge generated through this study would provide an effective knowledge base for training of Oral Literature teachers in Kenya on how to use audio-visual instructional resource in teaching and learning Oral Literature.

4. Review of Literature

4.1 Teachers' Competence in Utilization of Audio-Visual Resources

Moody (1984) noted the value of literature can only arise if the subject is properly understood by both teachers and students. This is important because it has been established that there is a high correlation between what teachers know and what they teach (Wilson et al., 1987). Thus, the ability to teach Oral Literature effectively depends on the teachers' knowledge, and knowledge occurs in a variety of forms. Teacher effectiveness is impeded if the teacher is unfamiliar with the body of knowledge taught and that teachers' effectiveness is subject specific. The implication of this for teachers is that they must thoroughly understand the content of what they teach.

Okwara et al., (2008) report that the two curriculum developers interviewed revealed that they assumed that English and Literature are inseparable and they expect the teachers to teach without any problem. From the above research it is evident that

Oral Literature is often taught by teachers who have little or no prior training in literature and therefore may have no interest or knowledge of the relevant instructional aids appropriate for the learning process. These teachers will therefore acquire material to enable learners pass exams but not acquire required skills. To enable learners derive maximum benefit from Oral Literature, there is need for educators to and motivate organize the learning experiences the learners by making learning more realistic and participatory, based on appropriate teaching-learning resources for Oral Literature because, Oral Literature is a genre that aesthetically educates citizens on their cultural and National Heritage. It therefore unites the citizens as it is passed from generation to generation and links current and emerging issues. Digolo (1997) reported that lack of competence among some music teachers hindered proper utilization of the instructional resources.

Research by Brunning et al., (1999) concluded that teachers' characteristics such as personal teaching efficacy, modelling and enthusiasm, caring and high expectation are associated with increase in students' achievement or academic performance. High levels of learning may occur as well as learners feeling good about themselves and the resource materials used by teachers during instructional time. Learning takes place with ease and faster under teachers that are well organized, relative to essential teaching resources. Farrant (2002) observed that the type of resources used by teachers and the way teachers interact with students influences their learning. To promote order and learning in the classroom every teacher should possess essential teaching skills. No one can teach something to someone without doing it in some particular way, and that way of teaching has significant effects on the entire teaching and learning situation (Farrant, 2002).

Ehintero and Ajibade (2000) posit that teaching is a process of continuous personal development and professional self-discovery alongside an emerging understanding of the teaching / learning process and resources. Communication based on appropriate multimedia services is an essential art in good teaching. This is because effective teaching cannot occur without the use of diverse styles inclusive of oral or sign language communication (Mukwa, 2003). The teacher whose understanding of topic is thorough use clearer language, their discourse is more connected, and they provide better explanation than those whose background is weaker and makes proper choice of teaching and learning resources. The way the students perceive the teachers in terms of their (teachers) knowledge of content of subject matter may significantly affect the students' academic performance. According to Okwara et al., (2008) pedagogical content knowledge depends on an understanding of a particular topic and how to explain it in a way that it will make sense to the students. Pedagogical content knowledge implies, an understanding of ways of representing the subject that make it comprehensible to others and an understanding of what makes the learning of specific

topics easy or difficult. Eggen and Kauchak (2001) assert that, where pedagogical content knowledge is lacking, teachers commonly paraphrase information in learners' textbooks or provide abstract explanations that are not meaningful to their students. From evidence available in literatures, it is being established why teachers' knowledge of subject matter is highly essential for effective teaching.

Ehindero (1990) confirmed that a teachers' teaching is influenced by the level of his pedagogical knowledge, as different from his subject matter knowledge. It is noteworthy that pedagogical knowledge is not exactly the same thing as knowledge of subject matter, the two are nevertheless, intimately linked, because the teachers' mastery and use of them in the classroom will indicate the depth of their knowledge of subject matter. Okwara et al., (2008) reported that 60% of the Kenyan high school English teachers were neither trained nor prepared to teach English as an integrated subject. The remaining 40% had trained to teach either English or Literature but combined with different subjects. This is evident from the requirement sometimes that Kiswahili teachers teach Literature in English which questions their competency.

According to the Syambo and Mazrui (1992), Oral Literature is presented through words, mouth and actions. This was reinforced by drums and other musical instruments though written literature introduced changes, the emerging technology in media like radio, video, audiotapes, televisions and cinema have reinforced the need of using available resources. The teacher should therefore be a guide in the learning process. According to them instructional resources categorized into print materials which include the syllabus, reference books, encyclopaedia, journals, magazine and newspapers. Non Print materials like audio visual materials, computers, films, slides, tapes, radio, cartoons, charts, diagrams, TV, videos and many others. Community resources include resource persons, field trips, cultural events, and libraries. Realia and its representation; this category includes real objects, exhibits museums, dioramas & panorama (Muchilwa 1998).

Luvisia (2003) found that the teachers had appositive attitude towards the use of learning resources yet they are not applying a variety of the available instructional resources, he particularly noted over dependence on KIE course books and chalkboards. On the use of appropriate books in teaching, Stitles (2008) recommended the use of available instructional resources so long they are utilized under well stipulated timeframe. He also noted efficiency in this individualized type of teaching/learning. However, Dow (1998) notes that publishers have altered format and content of these materials to reflect the contemporary recreational requirements of youth most of whom are raised in an era of electronic entertainment. Mbuthia (1996) noted that when pictures and cartons are used as an integrated package of instruction in Oral Literature teaching, the amount of information is enhanced and retained. He recommends the use of visual media in instructional process as it enhance analysis, synthesis and evaluative

skills. These are important in Oral Literature which is by nature an orally formulated, transmitted and performed art. According to Finnegan (1970) there is no mystery about the idea that Oral Literature is manifested through oral composition, performance and oral transmission. It therefore stresses the need of using available resources.

Zeichner (1992) has summarized the extensive literature that describes successful teaching approaches for diverse populations. He made several assertions about appropriate strategies for delivering Oral Literature instruction. They include the fact that: Instruction focuses on students' creation of meaning about content in an interactive and collaborative learning environment. Teachers avoid repetitive rote learning but instead, involve learners in novel problem-solving activities. Teachers expose learners to challenging activities. They ask open-ended questions requiring students to use their judgment and form opinions. They choose activities where students must use analytic skills, evaluate, and make connections. They expect students to conduct research, complete their homework, and manage their time effectively

4.2 Teachers Improvisation of Instructional Resources

Lebusa (1981), in her study on teaching strategies involving instructional materials in the teaching of Sesotho *reading in Standards One to Three*", recommended, that the teacher must: Scheme, plan and prepare carefully on the methods used should involve the students more in preparation and use of instructional materials. A second study that looked at instructional materials in language was by Kiganda (1980). The main objective of the study was to produce and evaluate a sample instructional material for new English Syllabus for secondary schools. The instructional materials proposed new approaches to the teaching of English as an integrated subject and their suitability in divergent environments e.g. well-equipped classrooms and poorly equipped classrooms. Kiganda (1980) discovered that: The students' response to the material was generally good. The majority of students identified with that with training it are possible for teachers to produce their own instructional materials that are relevant to their teaching needs. Nkamba's study calls for relevant instructional materials in classrooms in Africa. Too often one finds schools struggling to purchase expensive materials such as the cuisainnair rods or imported abacus for use in teaching mathematics when there are many relevant materials.

Somjee, as quoted by Okombo, et al., (2008) reports that the objective characters, activities and environmental setting of the feature story in the material. The instructional objectives were largely, but not fully achieved and the teachers notes proved fairly useful, though not absolutely essential to the teachers. It can be concluded from Kiganda's study of ethnic instructional materials is transmission of aesthetic emotions while Oral Literature assists to transmit it through metaphors. Eshiwani (1983) in his study "Crowded Classrooms in Kenya" investigated the extent to which

instructional materials are available to the classroom teacher and how he utilizes the materials. He found that out of the classes that were surveyed 96% had one or more chalkboards; 75% of the blackboards were for writing on with chalk. Surprisingly less than 50% (45.8%) of the teachers possessed white makes chalk and only 37% had coloured chalk. A few classrooms (37%) had blackboards for writing on with special markers. On average, teachers write on the blackboard between 5 and 10 times a day. The blackboard is perhaps the most used visual aid in teaching in the primary school in Kenya. Pre-service and in-service training of teachers should take cognizant of this is to ensure that teachers are well prepared to use this seemingly important aid -the chalkboard.

Eshiwani (1986) in a study on the extent of availability and utilization of instructional resources in primary schools in Kenya revealed that there was a major gap in research on the effect of instructional materials on the learning of such subjects as mathematics, science and social studies. The population included primary teachers and its setting for the study was Kenya. Regarding instructional resources, it revealed the only media used included majorly the chalkboard and to an extent the whiteboard. He lamented that performance in mathematics has continued to be disappointingly poor in the African region which, possibly attributable to poor quality of teachers, was explainable mainly non-availability of appropriate instructional aids. Studies reviewed revealed that there is a major gap in research on the effect of instructional materials on such subjects as mathematics, science and social studies.

Ogoma (1987) researched on the availability of instructional resources in Social Studies in Nairobi and reported inadequacy in schools due to time for preparation funds and relevant material amongst others. A research by Kafue (2009) on the availability and utilization of non-projected instructional media revealed that the media were available in schools in low quantities and in poor states. The researcher recommended establishment of resource centers and the education ministry's improvement on the quality of teachers through teachers' professional colleges. Otieno (1989) researched on the acquisition of teaching aids in home science and reported that there were inadequate teaching aids, which were underutilized by the teachers. Both teachers and students did not improvise instructional resources.

Brown et al., (1985) suggested that teachers who would like their learners to excel must repair their own learning resources. He also said that seeking and finding resources that produce results when students use educational media gives satisfaction to teachers and learners and motivates them. Fraser (Schaefer, 1994) reported that parents may helping the preparation of instructional resources e.g. the library, collect material for project, craft and other skills, repair others gather information and help slow learners. Tomlinson (1989) asserted that teachers must provide the most effective means of stimulating interest and promoting understanding by use of diverse

instructional resources. Kembo–Sure (1994) asserted that Kenya is heterogeneous and literature instructional resources assist learners to acquire the national goals of national and international unity and appreciation of other people's culture. Sampath et al., (1990) revealed that learning depends on the senses. 83% is learnt and retained through sight 11% through hearing, 4% through smell and 1% through touch.

5. Materials and Methods

The study was conducted in Butere Sub County in Kakamega County, Kenya. The study target area consisted of 25 public secondary schools. The research design adopted for this paper was survey research approach. This design was considered appropriate for the study because it facilitates collection of a wide range of information or data from a large population with different characteristic and from different geographical backgrounds (Fraenkel & Wallen, 2002). The target population for the research involved oral literature teachers (75) and 25 headteachers. Morgan and Krejcie table was used to select the sample size for the study. In selecting teachers, proportionate stratified random sampling was used to select 63 out of 75 Oral literature teachers. The teachers were classified into two stratas based on the education zones the come from. For example, 40 OL teachers came from West Zone and 35 OL teachers came from East Zone. For headteachers, purposive sampling was used. A questionnaire was developed for the Oral Literature teachers based on the objectives of the study. This was referred to as Oral Literature Teachers Questionnaires (OLTQ). The interview schedule was designed to get headteachers opinion towards teachers' knowledge and skills in utilisation and improvisation of instructional resources in teaching and learning Oral Literature in secondary schools. The research instruments were tested for reliability and validity before they were administered to the field. Data collected was analysed using descriptive statistics (frequencies and percentages). This was done with the help of computer packages (Statistical package for social sciences [SPSS Version 16] and Ms. Excel 2007 software). Tables, pie charts, bar graphs and histograms were used to present quantitative data. Qualitative data from interviews was analysed using content analysis where responses were presented using narrative format as Neumann (2007) argues that it best enables them to retain a richness and authenticity from their original data sources (for example individual personal stories or events in ethnographies or specific historical events). In simple terms, the narrative is story telling/thematic content analysis.

6. Results

6.1 Demographic information of respondents

The demographic characteristics of respondents are general information of respondents that the study wanted to find from respondents (teachers) based on their gender, academic qualification, professional qualification, teaching experience and English and Oral Literature teaching experience.

6.1.1 Gender of teachers

The respondents were asked to indicate their gender; the results are given in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Respondents gender

The results show that 37(59%) of respondents were male Oral Literature while 26(41%) were female. The result indicated that the number of male language teachers surpasses that of female.

6.1.2 Academic Qualification of Oral Literature teachers

The study wanted to find out respondents academic qualifications. Their results are presented in Table 1.

Table 1: Academic qualification

Level	Frequency	Percent
BED	61	96.8
MED	1	1.6
Diploma	1	1.6
Total	63	100.0

The findings show that 61(96.8%) of respondents have Bachelor of Education arts degree as opposed to 2 (3.2%) who indicated that they have Masters in Education degree or Diploma qualification levels. Therefore, the result suggests that majority of respondents' degree academic qualifications therefore justifying their capability in teaching Oral Literature in secondary schools within Butere district.

6.2 Oral Literature Teaching Experience

Oral Literature teacher teaching experience is another indicator of determining their exposure in using audio-visual instructional methodologies in teaching and learning. This is because; in the questionnaire some teachers indicated that they trained in Kiswahili and Literature and therefore could not teach the integrated English subject but were capable of teaching literature alone. The respondents were asked to indicate their oral literature teaching experience. The results are displayed in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Oral Literature Teaching Experience

The findings show that 31.7% had taught OL between 1 – 5 years, 30.2% said that they have been teaching between 6 – 10 years, 19% said that they have experience spanning 11 – 15 years, 15.9% had between 16 – 20 years while only 3.2% had more than 9 years of experience in teaching Oral Literature. The result implies that majority of respondents had less than 10 years teaching OL in secondary schools therefore they could have enough understanding of the use of audio-visual devices in teaching the subject in secondary schools.

6.3 Teachers' knowledge and skills in developing & utilizing audio-visual instructional resources in teaching and learning Oral Literature

This is the third objective of the study that sought to determine English and Literature teacher knowledge and skills in developing and utilizing audio-visual instructional media in school. The results of the study are presented in sub-sections below:

A. Teacher's Subjects Trained in College

The teachers were asked to give a combination of subjects they were trained in during the time they were in the university. This could determine if they have the requisite knowledge and skills in utilizing audio-visual instructional media. The results are given in Table 2.

Table 2: Teachers subjects trained in college

Subject	Frequency	Percent
English and Literature	52	82.5
English and Kiswahili	6	9.5
English and C.R.E.	4	6.3
Literature and French	1	1.6
Total	63	100.0

The result show that most 52(82.5%) are trained in English and Literature, 6(9.5%) said that they have been trained in English and Kiswahili, 4(6.3%) said that they were trained in English and C.R.E. while only 1(1.6%) indicated that they were trained in Literature and French studies. the result therefore implies that most teachers surveyed had trained in English and literature suggesting that they do have understanding of the utilisation of audio-visual instructional materials in teaching and learning Oral Literature.

B. Nature of training received at college

The respondents were further asked to indicate the nature of training that they received while they were in college. The findings are given in Figure 3

Figure 3: Nature of Training Received in College

The result show that majority 40(63%) were trained to teach English and Literature as integrated while 23(37%) said that they were not trained to teach English and Literature as integrated. the result suggest that those who were taught English and Literature separately could have enough have enough knowledge and skills in using audio-visual devices as opposed to those who were trained to teach English and Literature as integrated.

C. Characteristics of English and Literature Teachers

The study sought to determine the characteristics of English and Literature teacher so as to get understanding of how he/she utilised audio-visual instructional resources in teaching and learning Oral Literature in schools. The respondents were supposed to indicate their level of agreement on a five point Likert scale; Strongly Disagree – 1, Disagree – 2, Undecided – 3, Agree – 4 and Strongly Agree – 5. The summaries of results are presented in Table 3.

Table 3: Characteristics of English and Literature Teachers

	Excellent		Good		Satisfactory		Not satisfactory		Total	
	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%
I take interest in my profession	37	58.7	24	38.1	2	3.2	0	0.0	63	100.0
I have command over the content of the subject	33	52.4	26	41.3	2	3.2	2	3.2	63	100.0
I manage the course contents for the whole academic year	15	23.8	41	65.1	6	9.5	1	1.6	63	100.0
I present the lesson through interesting activities	16	25.4	45	71.4	2	3.2	0	0.0	63	100.0
I come in the class well prepared	27	42.9	36	57.1	0	0.0	0	0.0	63	100.0
I motivate the students to make the lesson interesting	14	22.2	47	74.6	2	3.2	0	0.0	63	100.0

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I evaluate the homework daily	3	4.8	36	57.1	23	36.5	1	1.6	63	100.0
I maintain the discipline of the classroom	26	41.3	35	55.6	2	3.2	0	0.0	63	100.0
I take care of students seating arrangement	21	33.3	35	55.6	5	7.9	2	3.2	63	100.0
I develop valid test in students use of audio-visual teaching resources	0	0	25	39.6	28	44.4	10	15.9	63	100.0
I give individual attention to the students	3	4.8	34	53.9	25	39.7	1	1.6	63	100.0
I do appropriate assessment during the lesson	9	14.3	46	73	8	12.7	0	0.0	63	100.0
I have developed reading culture in my class	15	23.8	38	60.3	10	15.9	0	0.0	63	100.0

The result shows that most teachers have positive characteristics towards English and Literature as shown in the results above. The positive characteristics that teacher has towards English and Literature thereby explaining their adoption and use of audio-visual instructional resources.

D. Reasons for Respondents Teaching Oral Literature

The study wanted to find the basis to which the respondents were teaching Oral Literature in schools. This could influence the extent to which they utilise audio – visual instructional resources in teaching and learning Oral Literature. The respondents were asked to give reasons as to why they are teaching Oral Literature, their responses are given in Table 4.

Table 4: Reasons for respondents teaching Oral Literature

Reasons	Frequency	Percent
I opted it by my own choice	37	58.7
I have a sound background knowledge of OL	21	33.3
There is no other teacher of Oral Literature	5	7.9
Total	63	100.0

It is clear that 37(58.7%) said that they opted to teach Oral Literature on their own, 21(33.3%) said that they had a sound background knowledge of Oral Literature while 5(7.9%) said that they teach Oral Literature because there is no other teacher within their school. the finding implies that the teachers are not forced to teach Oral Literature because of the circumstances as school but it was their own career choice. however this does not reflect on their utilisation of audio-visual instructional resource use in teaching the subject.

E. Whether teachers were taught how to use audio-visual instructional resources in teaching and learning Oral Literature

The respondents were asked whether they were ever taught how to use audio-visual instructional resources in teaching and learning Oral Literature. The results are given in Figure 4.

Figure 4: Teachers Knowledge in audio – visual Instructional Use

The result show that majority 40(63%) of respondents agreed that they were taught how to use audio-visual devices in schools while 23(37%) said that they were never taught. the result suggest that non – utilization of audio-visual instructional resources could be a factor explaining it low usage in schools within Butere District.

F. Teachers Improvisation of Audio-visual Instructional Resources

As one of the indicators of Oral Literature teachers' knowledge and skills, they were asked whether they improvised audio-visual instructional resources in teaching and learning of Oral Literature, their results are given in Table 5.

Table 5: Teachers' improvisation of audio-visual instructional materials

Frequency	Frequency	Percent
Rarely	34	54.0
Occasionally	18	28.6
Never	9	14.3
Always	2	3.2
Total	63	100.0

The findings show that 34(54%) of respondents rarely improvise audio-visual instructional materials, 18(28.6%) said that they occasionally did, 9(14.35) said that they have never improvised these resources while 2(3.2%) indicated that they always improvise audio-visual resources in teaching and learning Oral Literature in secondary

schools. therefore the results agrees with previous findings where teachers did not involve students in improving audio-visual instructional resources in teaching and learning Oral Literature.

G. Frequency of Use of Audio-Visual Instructional Resources

The study has so far established that audio-visual instructional materials are inadequate in schools. The study further asked teachers how frequent did they use the available audio-visual instructional resources in teaching and learning Oral Literature as part of determining their knowledge and skills in them. the results of the analysis are illustrated in Figure 5.

Figure 5: Frequency of use of audio-visual instructional resources

The results show that 58.7% rarely use audio-visual resources in teaching and learning Oral Literature, 34.9% said that they occasionally used, 4.8% said that they never used while 1.6% said that they always use instructional media resources in teaching and learning Oral Literature in secondary schools. The result agrees with previous findings where audio-visual instructional resources in teaching and learning Oral Literature was found to be low, this could have significant impact on students learning.

H. Difficulties faced in teaching Oral Literature

The respondents were also asked to indicate whether they faced any difficulties in teaching and learning Oral Literature in schools. Their responses are given in Table 6.

Table 6: Difficulties faced in teaching Oral Literature

Difficulty	Frequency	Percent
Curriculum is overloaded	49	77.8
Contents are not relevant to practical life	8	12.7
Curriculum cannot be completed in academic year	6	9.5
Total	63	100.0

The main difficulty that teachers face is that curriculum is overloaded (77.8%), followed by 12.7% of them who said that contents are not relevant to practical life while 9.5% said that Oral Literature curriculum cannot be completed in one academic year.

7. Discussions

At first, the study wanted to find out the subjects the teachers were trained in while they were still in college, from the results, majority were found to have learned English and Literature as integrated with others saying that they learnt English and Kiswahili and others indicating that they learnt Literature and French while in college. The findings suggest that the teachers were trained in college English and Literature as integrated thereby suggesting that they did not take literature subject as a whole but as a combination with other subjects, this could explain their low utilisation in schools. Another observation made by the study was that 63% of respondents indicated that they were taught how to use these audio-visual instructional resources in teaching and learning Oral Literature while 37% said they were never taught using these resources in teaching and learning Oral Literature. The results differ with Oure (1985) study that showed that most teachers in Amagoro District did not have requisite knowledge and skills in utilizing audio-visual resources. On the reasons as to why they learn Oral Literature in schools, most of the teachers indicated that they have sound background knowledge of Oral Literature, some indicated that they opted it by their own while a small number indicated that there were forced to teach the subject since there was no any other Oral Literature within their school. The findings also could have effect on the utilisation level of these devices as teachers who are not grounded well in Oral Literature could face difficulties in using audio-visual devices in teaching and learning Oral Literature in secondary schools. Difficulties encountered in teaching and learning Oral Literature could be a factor that will determine whether teachers will adopt the same in teaching and learning of the subject within their classrooms. Results indicate that majority said the difficulties they faced were; curriculum is usually overloaded (77.8%) making them not to effectively complete the same within the right frame of time. Other indicated that some contents of Oral Literature are not practicable in real life situations while 9.5% said that Oral Literature curriculum cannot be completed in one

academic year. these difficulties experienced by teachers could explain their non – utilisation in schools. Teachers' responses on frequency of use of audio visual instructional resources showed that 58.7% of them rarely used these with 34.9% indicating that they occasionally used these resources. Other respondents indicated that they rarely used while another said that they never use these instructional resources in teaching and learning Oral Literature in secondary schools. The result also agrees with previous results where audio-visual resources utilisation was found to be low or average on most schools surveyed by the research. The English teachers characteristics were found to be positive thereby suggesting that they engaged learners in classroom activities like; having command of the content of the subject, they present Oral Literature content through the whole academic year, they evaluate students homework daily and they maintain discipline in classrooms amongst other characteristics suggesting that teachers possess positive characteristics in classroom suggesting that the availability of these instructional resources in schools could make them use them in teaching and learning Oral Literature in secondary schools.

8. Conclusions and Recommendations

The teacher knowledge and skills was found to be adequate considering that over 90% of them had undergraduate degrees in Education (Arts) and most of them had taught English and Literature between 1 – 20 years. The study noted that improvisation of these audio-visual instructional materials was still low. The findings showed that students were rarely involved in improvising these audio-visual instructional resources and are supported with the fact that most teachers indicated that they also rarely improvised these audio-visual instructional resources in teaching and learning Oral Literature in secondary schools within Butere District. Lack of improvisation of these teaching and learning resources was a factor that explained the low utilisation of these devices in teaching and learning Oral Literature in secondary schools. This is despite the fact that the respondents indicated that 63% said that they were taught how to utilise these audio-visual instructional resources in teaching and learning Oral Literature in schools. Headteachers need to advise English teachers to create time for OL teaching using audio-visual resources as required in the integrated English syllabus. The headteachers need to motivate teachers to undergo in-service training on audio-visual instructional resources use. Government needs also to recruit more English teachers in secondary schools.

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